

success story

EIFFEL project results disseminated through Climate ADAPT

The Climate ADAPT platform strives to assist governments, authorities and decision makers from Europe in adapting to the impacts of climate change, providing accessible information and quality checked data, and assisting in the dissemination of information, programmes, projects and news (among others) related to new discoveries about climate change adaptation. Climate ADAPT supports several possibilities for communicating adaptation efforts, such as: Adaptation Options, Case Studies, Events, Guidance Documents, Information Portals, News, Organisations, Publications and Reports, Research and Knowledge Projects, and Tools. The EIFFEL project seeks to disseminate the products developed and facilitate their access to authorities and decision-makers in different European countries. Climate ADAPT (CA) is a very suitable platform to contribute to this dissemination. Therefore, six entries have been submitted to the CA platform to share what has been developed by different teams and covering different topics, all of them related to climate change adaptation responses developed through the EIFFEL project. Some of these entries have already been accepted and published on the platform, while others are in the process of being verified by the portal's internal evaluation committee.

One entry describing the EIFFEL project purpose has been submitted and is currently published on the platform [here](#). Five other entries are under evaluation: one from Pilot 1 as a Case Study, describing in detail the objectives, challenges and main results developed. Two Tools entries were also sent corresponding to the tools developed in Pilot 2, both the Bare Soil Identification tool and the Land Suitability Tool. At the same time, for Pilot 5 an entry has been created to disseminate the portal www.waterinfo.fi that constantly updates the water situation in Finland, in which Eiffel has participated in the extension of the portal's mapping tool with information on drought conditions. Finally, best type of entry for the afforestation study is under discussion with CA responsible and EIFFEL developing team. This study explored the conversion of agricultural land to forests, showing improvements in water levels, indicating greater water sustainability and better response to floods. Both EIFFEL project and Climate Adapt benefit from the publication of these entries. Nevertheless, to ensure the quality of the published entries, CA publication process needs an experts' review. This is leading to a longer process than the initially expected and informed (from days to more than a month). Thus, our recommendation for those interested in contributing to this portal would be to considerate this extended time frame when starting the process

Useful links:

www.eiffel4climate.eu

<https://www.eiffel4climate.eu/index.php/pilots>

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 eiffel4climate project

#climatechange